

Tit-Bits of nanoparticle synthesis[†]

Tarasankar Pal

Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur-721 302, West Bengal, India

E-mail : tpal@chem.iitkgp.ernet.in

Abstract : Modern microscopes and spectroscopes have revolutionized the monitoring techniques. That is why the nanoparticles especially metal nanoparticles (MNPs) have become attractive and find innumerable applications in the wide world. Synthesis and stabilization of MNPs relates to physical and chemical processes while the later govern basic thermodynamics and kinetics. Precise control over the size and morphology and the understanding of particle growth need new theory of crystallization. This is achievable when basic fact of chemical interaction is understood.

Synthesis of metal nanoparticle (MNP) has now come up in a big way. This has become possible mainly because of the remarkable advancement in the field of spectroscopy and microscopy. Powerful trump of these instruments lies with excellent magnification to resolve images of the particles. Thus one can visualize metal nanoparticles almost with atomic resolution. Simple optical microscope cannot image MNPs as visible light with its long wavelength does not interact with tiny MNPs but electron beam can do. So we easily image MNPs. The particles, if manipulated with care, can revolutionize the world of synthesis, catalysis, spectroscopy, biomedical field, optoelectronic devices etc. It is still a difficult proposition to obtain MNP of comparable size, shape or morphology which is essential for necessary nano technological applications. A big problem indeed! A physical method to separation is definitely a way out to have MNP of similar size but even then the method cannot cater the market need and so remains intuitive. The so called 'bottom up' approach to obtain gram quantity of MNP faces a challenge and may be looked in the perspective of chemistry at hand.

Slow and fast reduction kinetics of precursor compounds may be considered from a different angle. Slow process always inherits autocatalytic growth (may be represented by sigmoidal curve)¹ resulting in large particle. Often times fast kinetics suffers from the dearth of supply of metal ions from the bulk solution and hence produces smaller MNPs. Boiling a solution of sodium citrate and HAuCl₄ (Fren's method) produce Au(0) particles with

tight size distribution². Unique examples for producing Au nanoparticles with tight size distribution has been demonstrated out of refluxing condition which has become digestive ripening (Fig. 1a)³ and which is the offset of the well-known, Ostwald ripening process (Fig. 1b)⁴. Standard reduction potential of the reducing agent (E^0 value) matters for the preparation of metal nanoparticles from the bottom up technique. Thus faster nucleation produces smaller particles which is similar to the case where a stronger reducing agent is used. Here nucleation takes place all at a time like the fast reaction kinetics. Thus at room temperature NaBH₄ evolve smaller Ag NPs (say Creighton sol⁵) whereas ascorbic acid produces larger Ag nanoparticles⁶. It may be born in mind that higher pH condition makes ascorbic acid a stronger reducing agent and so is true for reducing sugars also⁷.

An increasingly deserving approach employing galvanic replacement reactions/transmetallation reactions (Fig. 2)⁸ has recently become a key and novel means towards syntheses of a broad spectrum of hollow/porous metal nanoframeworks, metal alloy nanostructures, etc. This single step methodology is based on the sacrificial oxidative dissolution of a reactive (less noble) metal template by a suitable metal salt and the process is solely driven by their distinctly different reduction potential values and finally come up with reductive deposition of the nobler element from the precursor salt. A group of materials' research community has exploited the technique both in aqueous and organic media to design engineered

[†]In honour of Professor M. C. Chattopadhyaya on the occasion of his 70th birth anniversary.

Fig. 1. Ostwald ripening (a) and digestive ripening (b)^{4b}.

Fig. 2. A schematic diagram of galvanic replacement reactions between Ni^{2+} and $\text{Al}(\text{s})$.

nanomaterials with intriguing properties but till date, a major part of the area is confined with the decoration of monometallic/hybrid nanocomposites but made up largely with Au, Ag, Pd and Pt⁸⁻¹⁰. Few reports have also been highlighted with Ru and Rh as one of the contributing components in the replacement reaction^{11,12}.

Higher temperature causes smaller MNP. This has a relation to faster kinetics also¹³. Two metal may mix together forming an alloy structure. In what proportion will the participating metals mix, all depends on their lattice matching. Silver and gold mix up in all proportion as their lattice parameters are almost similar. However, Sn and Ag alloy together till 3 wt. percent of Ag in Sn. After that phase separation of the two partners takes place. Higher percentage of Ag crystallizes in Sn matrix and a 'hetero-junction' appears. This hetero-junction has been found to have immense importance is catalysis, especially in plasmonic photocatalysis¹⁴.

Another structure may be core-shell architecture¹⁵. In the process one can save a precious metal also. An elegant example is $\text{Au}_{\text{core}} - \text{Ag}_{\text{shell}}$ particle. From thermodynamic consideration this architecture is easy to fabri-

cate. Taking preformed Au nanoparticles in solution as seed, Ag(0) shell can be added onto Au core just by slow reduction of added Ag^+ ions on the Au core (Fig. 3). A strong reducing agent has to be avoided to reduce the added Ag^+ ions. A strong reducing agent in solution instead of putting shell on Au(0) seed, might bring separated Ag(0) nanoparticles causing Au(0) and Ag(0) mixed dispersion. UV-Visible spectroscopic measurement easily short out the problem of core-shell and mixed dispersion easily¹⁵. One can fabricate $\text{Ag}_{\text{core}} - \text{Au}_{\text{shell}}$ particle (inverted core-shell particle) bringing the kinetic control of reaction. In this case Ag(0) particles would serve the purpose of seed and the added Au^{3+} ions have to be reduced onto Ag(0) particles. In this process there is enough possibility of oxidation of Ag(0) by Au^{3+} ions as Au is nobler than silver. So kinetics of added Au^{3+} reduction by a reducing agent has to be very fast so that Au^{3+} ion cannot oxidize Ag(0) nanoparticles¹⁶. Thus $\text{Ag}_{\text{core}} - \text{Au}_{\text{shell}}$ particle can results in and that is known as inverted core-shell particle. It may be spelt out that always normal core-shell structure results in from the thermodynamic consideration and noble metal lie as a core.

Fig. 3. Au_{core} – Ag_{shell} and Ag_{core} – Au_{shell} particle^{15,16}.

Concentration of precursor compound matters. Ready supply of available metal ions always causes larger particle formation during reduction¹⁷. Low temperature reduction related to Arrhenius way to explain the product formation. Reduction rate may be doubled or trebled for every ten degree rise in temperature causing smaller and smaller MNPs. So high temperature reduction means evolution of small particles (Table 1)¹⁸.

Table 1. Effect of temperature on the sodium citrate sol for the preparation Au NPs

Temperature (°C)	Approximate time for the completion of reaction (min)	Mean particle size (Angstrom)
100	5	200
80	25	165

Manipulation and sequence of addition¹⁹ of a reagent for the evolution of particles from solution plays an important role in MNP synthesis. It is always paradoxical that solution of HgCl₂ addition to dilute SnCl₂ solution causes silky white Hg₂Cl₂ precipitation in one case. In another case metallic Hg gets precipitated. In the first case addition of HgCl₂ solution has to be introduced all at time into the SnCl₂ solution not in portion. Otherwise black Hg particles are produced with drop by drop introduction of HgCl₂ solution. Drop wise addition causes a reaction with a very low concentration of HgCl₂ embraces larger no. of Sn²⁺ ions. So, Hg²⁺ reduces to Hg(0). On the other hand large amount of HgCl₂ (while added all at a time) encounter comparatively small no. of Sn²⁺ ions in solution. This is described as follows :

Presence of capping agent^{20a} during the bottom up synthesis of MNP can easily controls the growth of particle. Capping agent lays a physical barrier surrounding a particle or there a specific plane of a growing crystal may be capped. So in the first case particles do not grow after nucleation due to a physical barrier created by the capping agent and in the second case a particular plane may not grow further (Fig. 4)^{20b}. Thus one can lead the growth of an uncapped crystal plane intentionally just keeping a selective plane capped. This is called MNP growth in a particular direction through oriented attachment protocol²¹. Hence, MNP growth can be restricted selectively using

Fig. 4. Selective capping of the {111} facets of Rh seed particles with citrate and then temperature-dependent diffusion of Rh from corner to edge^{20b}.

facet selective capping agent. Thus, restricted growth of MNPs brings steps, kinks, stages etc. with high and low index facets which improve catalytic rates. Here the longer chain of the capping agent may encapsulate the particles from all sides and then the particles impart the property of the capping agent in solvent. Thus particles with long hydrophobic chain becomes soluble in organic solvent²². Otherwise hydrosol in water or polar solvents are produced as Michael Faraday, Fren, Creighton and many others observed. Affinity of donor atoms in a capping agent plays a crucial role.

Length of the capping agent and also the charge on it changes the property of the grown MNP. ‘Hard’ and ‘Soft’ acid base (HSAB) character of the donor atoms is important. It is known that softer Au nanoparticle prefer to bind with thiols and softer Ag preferentially binds with amines²³. Facile reduction of a metal ion is possible if the metal ion remains free in solution²⁴. Cation exchange resin bound Ni²⁺ is difficult to reduce which is otherwise easy while present in aqueous solution. As an extension of this propo-

sition has been reported recently for the reduction of Pd²⁺ in the interface of two immiscible solvents²⁵. Silver mirror formation on glass surface is an age old observation. The nucleation of Ag(0) is again can be explained as a matrix driven phenomenon. The initial nucleation takes place at the water-air interface, on a clean glass surface, in a test tube or at point on a glass surface with a deliberately created surface defect²⁶. The reagent for silver mirror formation being simple glucose and Tollens reagent. In this regard homogeneous precipitation Ni²⁺-dimethylglyoximate precipitation by urea correlates for bigger crystallite formation. Otherwise ammonia brings smaller rose red crystals where heterogeneous precipitation takes place if ammonia is introduced from outside. Cylindrical Rh nanorod preparation has been reported from microwave (MW) digestion in a record time of 90 s. There cetyltrimethyl ammonium bromide (CTAB) from MW produces ammonia that brings required pH and undecomposed CTAB, a growth directing agent, stabilizes Rh nanorods.

Some metals crystallize in different geometrical shapes. This process can be controlled but metals inherit their own geometrical structures. Alfred Werner could not recognize metal-metal bonding in compounds as is now easily revealed from X-ray diffraction studies. We have metal nanoparticles (~100 nm) sometimes with rich plasmon bands with inherited dimensionality and we have fluorescing metal clusters (sub-nanometer Cu, Ag, Au etc. particles) in chemistry (sub-nanometer particles) also²⁷⁻²⁹.

References

1. L. Becucci, M. R. Moncelli and R. Guidelli, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2003, **125**, 3784.
2. G. Frens, *Nat. Phys. Sci.*, 1973, **20**, 241.
3. B. L. V. Prasad, S. I. Stoeva, C. M. Sorensen and K. J. Klabunde, *Chem. Mater.*, 2003, **15**, 935.
4. (a) W. Ostwald, *Phys. Chem.*, 1901, **37**, 385; (b) D. S. Sidhaye and B. L. V. Prasad, *New J. Chem.*, 2011, **35**, 755.
5. J. A. Creighton, C. G. Blatchford and M. G. Albrecht, *J. Chem. Soc., Farad. Trans. 2*, 1979, **75**, 790.
6. K. P. Velikov, G. E. Zegers and A. V. Blaaderen, *Langmuir*, 2003, **19**, 1384.
7. P. Raveendran, J. Fu and S. L. Wallen, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2003, **125**, 13940.
8. (a) Z. Gu, Q. Cui, J. Chen, J. Buckley, T. Ando, D. Erdeniz, P. Wong, A. Hadjiafxenti, P. Epaminonda, I. E. Gunduz, C. Rebholz and C. C. Doumanidis, *Surf. Coat. Tech.*, 2013, **215**, 493; (b) H.-L. Jiang, T. Akita, T. Ishida, M. Haruta and Q. Xu, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2011, **133**, 1304.
9. W. Yu, M. D. Porosoff and J. G. Chen, *Chem. Rev.*, 2012, **112**, 5780.
10. S. Guo, S. Dong and E. Wang, *ACS Nano*, 2010, **4**, 547.
11. K. Kusada, H. Kobayashi, T. Yamamoto, S. Matsumura, N. Sumi, K. Sato, K. Nagaoka, Y. Kubota and H. Kitagawa, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2013, **135**, 5493.
12. S. Xie, H. Zhang, N. Lu, M. Jin, J. Wang, M. J. Kim, Z. Xie and Y. Xia, *Nano Lett.*, 2013, **13**, 6262.
13. I. A. Rahman and V. Padavettan, *J. Nanometer.*, 2012, 132424.
14. J. Pal, A. K. Sasmal, M. Ganguly and T. Pal, *J. Phys. Chem. (C)*, 2015, **119**, 3780.
15. K. Mallik, M. Mandal, N. Pradhan and T. Pal, *Nano Lett.*, 2001, **1**, 319.
16. S. Pande, S. K. Ghosh, S. Praharaj, S. Panigrahi, S. Basu, S. Jana, A. Pal, T. Tsukuda and T. Pal, *J. Phys. Chem. (C)*, 2007, **111**, 10806.
17. K. Mallick, Z. L. Wang and T. Pal, *J. Photochem. Photobiol. A : Chem.*, 2001, **140**, 75.
18. J. Turkevich, P. C. Stevenson and J. Hillier, *Discuss. Faraday Soc.*, 1951, **11**, 55.
19. I. Ojea-Jimenez, N. G. Bastus and V. Puentes, *J. Phys. Chem. (C)*, 2011, **115**, 15752.
20. (a) S. Nath, S. Praharaj, S. Panigrahi, S. K. Ghosh, S. Kundu, S. Basu and T. Pal, *Langmuir*, 2005, **21**, 10405; (b) S. Xie, H. Zhang, N. Lu, M. Jin, J. Wang, M. J. Kim, Z. Xie and Y. Xia, *Nano Lett.*, 2013, **13**, 6262.
21. R. L. Penn and J. F. Banfield, *Science*, 1998, **281**, 969.
22. S. Praharaj, S. K. Ghosh, S. Nath, S. Kundu, S. Panigrahi, S. Basu and T. Pal, *J. Phys. Chem. (B)*, 2005, **109**, 13166.
23. S. Nath, S. K. Ghosh, S. Kundu, S. Praharaj, S. Panigrahi and T. Pal, *J. Nanopart. Res.*, 2006, **8**, 111.
24. C.-J. Jia and F. Schuth, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, 2011, **13**, 2457.
25. S. Dutta, S. Sarkar, C. Ray, A. Roy, R. Sahoo and T. Pal, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*, 2014, **6**, 9134.
26. A. K. Sinha, S. Jana, S. Pande, S. Sarkar, M. Pradhan, M. Basu, S. Saha, A. Pal and T. Pal, *CrystEngComm*, 2009, **11**, 1210.
27. M. Ganguly, A. Pal and T. Pal, *J. Phys. Chem. (C)*, 2011, **115**, 22138.
28. M. Ganguly, A. Pal, Y. Negishi and T. Pal, *Chem.-Euro. J.*, 2012, **18**, 15845.
29. M. Ganguly, A. Pal, Y. Negishi and T. Pal, *Langmuir*, 2013, **29**, 2033.